

**Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2025; Special Edition 2 – Low
Resource Settings: Commentary on Downing, J. et al.**

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2025 paper by Downing, J. et al., Reducing inequity in the provision of children's palliative care in low- and middle-income countries: A focus on education and research, published in Palliative Medicine.

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“Over 98% of the nearly 21 million children worldwide who could benefit from palliative care live in low and middle-income countries (LMICs), yet the majority of these settings lack pediatric palliative care (PPC) services, trained personnel or consistent access to essential medicines.”¹⁻⁴ This in itself, is an overwhelming paradox.

The editorial from Downing et al. (2025) addresses the persistent inequities in the provision of children’s palliative care in LMICs. The authors remind us that inequity in children’s palliative care is not merely a technical gap, but a reflection of broader social injustice. The article argues that reducing inequity requires more than expanding services; it demands intentional and equity-focused strategies that address structural, socioeconomic, and geographic barriers. The editorial highlights two priorities for reducing PPC inequity in resource-limited settings: strengthening education and training, and expanding locally generated research. The authors emphasize the importance of providing accessible PPC training models, empowering children’s palliative local leaders, developing equitable collaborations and mentorship to learn from each other. Also, there is a call for the “decolonization” of children’s palliative care and research through rebalancing power dynamics, intentionally hosting international conferences in LMICs with relevant content for all settings, establishing initiatives to reduce financial barriers, promoting equitable participation, and supporting local researchers, particularly when writing in other languages.

Blatman et al. (2025) interviews humanitarian healthcare professionals about their perspectives on children’s palliative care, and preferences and needs for training. A key finding from the study was the preference for virtual training on theoretical topics, and hands-on training for palliative care skills, particularly communication. The study also describes important health system barriers to training and implementing PPC that we also have in Latin America:

inadequate physical space within health facilities, a limited number of trained staff, and limited availability of opioids and other essential medicines.

In México, Ramos-Guerrero et al. (2025) analyzes the development of PPC using an adaptation of the World Health Organization's assessment model. The authors identify significant regulatory advances; however, they underscore a persistent gap between regulation and effective implementation, largely attributed to the fragmentation of the health system and the absence of a current national plan with allocated funding. Although there has been a progressive increase in pediatric palliative care teams, these remain insufficient and are concentrated mainly in highly specialized hospitals, with limited home and perinatal coverage. Also, the authors detail a barrier that many PPC physicians working in LMICs could relate with, access to essential medicines, particularly opioids, represents one of the main challenges due to low consumption, supply problems, a shortage of pediatric formulations, and prescription restrictions.

Houston, et al (2023) analyzes 112 institutions across 23 countries caring for children with cancer from low (LIC), lower-middle (LMIC), upper-middle (UMIC), and high (HIC) income levels. Their findings show that access to specialists varied by income level with 71% of HICs, 41% of UMICs, 32% of LMICs, and 17% of LICs reporting almost always having access to palliative care specialists. When it comes to the availability of oral morphine, it was reported to be always available in 100% of HICs, 76% of UMICs, 27% of LMICs, and 33% of LICs and injectable morphine in 100% of HICs, 96% of UMICs, 41% of LMICs, and 33% of LICs.

Personally, I find these results heartbreaking to read. The author's conclusion is a painful reality:

“Access to pediatric palliative care services varies by income level. Despite increased need for

palliative services in LMICs, there is less access to trained providers and essential medications, especially in those with decreased resources.”⁷

Downing et al. (2025) frames equity in children’s palliative care as a moral imperative - one that requires humility, shared responsibility, and global collaboration to ensure that no child is left to suffer without care. So, how do we reduce the inequity in children’s palliative provision in limited-resource countries?

For the past 16 years, I've worked as a PPC physician in Costa Rica, a LMIC with a privileged social healthcare system compared to other countries in Central America. When I met a dear colleague from a neighboring LIC, and we discussed our own barriers and limitations for providing quality care in our PPC programs, I realized I shouldn't complain, but rather be grateful. This meeting emphasized the realities of this inequity, and my perspective instantly changed forever.

Ultimately, all healthcare professionals who care for children and young people with life-threatening or life-limiting illnesses, regardless of the country they live in, should reflect on this question. We must encourage ourselves to actively participate in the answer, because outside our own reality or comfort zone, there will always be a colleague with fewer resources than us, who is required to adequately care for their patients and their families.

Additional References

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